

Increasing Trend of Enterobacter Species Infection in a Tertiary care Centre, Puducherry

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Abstract:

Introduction: Enterobacter species are gram negative bacilli belonging to Enterobacteriaceae family. Enterobacter spp are one of the most common bacteria to cause nosocomial infections. Multidrug Resistance (MDR) is on increasing trend among Enterobacter spp which leads to difficulty in treating the patients that would result in increased mortality and morbidity associated with Enterobacter spp infection.

Aims and Objectives: To determine the prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of Enterobacter spp isolated from pus samples over a period of 30 months.

Materials and Methods: This study was a cross sectional descriptive study. Enterobacter spp was identified based on standard biochemical tests. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was done for all isolates by Kirby Baeur Disk Diffusion test as per CLSI guidelines.

Results: Enterobacter spp infection was found to be increasing among pus samples and the antimicrobial resistance was also increasing to commonly used antibiotics and Multidrug resistance were also increasing trend.

Conclusion: Therefore, the monitoring of the trend of Enterobacter spp infection and its antimicrobial resistance pattern should be done and strengthening of Hospital infection control practices should be practiced in order to prevent the nosocomial spread of highly multidrug resistance bacteria and also in the community.

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Introduction

Enterobacter species are gram negative bacilli which is non sporing, facultative anaerobe belongs to Enterobacteriaceae family[1]. Enterobacter spp can cause urinary tract infections, Pneumonia, Bacteremia, wound infections, Central nervous system infections mainly in hospitalized patients [2]. Among the various species of Enterobacter, Enterobacter aerogenes and Enterobacter cloacae are mainly responsible for majority of infections caused by Enterobacter species[3]. Enterobacter infections are one of the most common bacteria to cause Nosocomial infections[1,3,4]. It is one of the leading cause of nosocomial infections caused by gram negative bacteria[5]. It is one of the ESKAPE (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* species) group of Pathogen to cause serious nosocomial infection. Antibiotic resistance is increasing in ESKAPE group of pathogens. Enterobacter is one among the Priority Pathogen list released by WHO in 2017 for new antimicrobial development on urgent basis as antibiotic resistance

is increasing among these bacteria[6,7]. Multidrug Resistance (MDR) is on increasing trend among Enterobacter which leads to difficulty in treating the patients that would result in increased mortality and morbidity associated with Enterobacter infection. Our study aims to determine the prevalence and antimicrobial sensitivity pattern of Enterobacter spp isolated from pus samples. This will help us to get information pertaining to empirical treatment of infections caused by Enterobacter.

Materials & Methods

Our study was a cross sectional descriptive study which included all Enterobacter spp isolated from pus samples in the Microbiology department from January 2017 to June 2019 at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Research Institute, Puducherry, India. Bacteria were identified by colony morphology, gram staining, standard biochemical test (IMViC) and sugar fermentation tests. Antibiotic susceptibility of bacteria was done in Muller Hinton agar by standard Kirby Bauer s disc diffusion test as per CLSI 2017 guidelines(CLSI).

Following antimicrobials were tested against all bacteria: Cephalosporin (Ceftriaxone); β lactam / β lactamase inhibitor (cefoperazone / sulbactam and Piperacillin / tazobactam); fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin); aminoglycosides (Amikacin and gentamicin); carbapenems (imipenam and meropenam); cotrimoxazole, polymyxins (polymyxin B, colistin). Quality control: Batch wise testing was done for all agar plates, biochemical test and antibiotic discs as per CLSI Guidelines. Bacterial strains ATCC Staphylococcus aureus 25923 and ATCC Escherichia coli 25922 were used for quality control purpose.

Statistical Analysis: The results were entered in Excel sheet and analyzed with frequency and ratio.

Results:

During the study period, totally 109 Enterobacter spp were isolated from pus samples. Figure 1 shows the year wise distribution of Enterobacter spp among pus samples. Majority of Entrobacter spp infection was found in age group of 41-60 years (33.94%) followed by 21-40years (29.35%), 22.01% were seen in age group of 61-80years, 11.92% were found among age group of less than 20years and only 2.75% from more than 80years. Males were found to have more infection with 64.22% compared to females with 35.77%.Majority of infection was in inpatients with 86.23% and only 13.76% were from outpatients. Table 1 shows age wise and gender distribution of Enterobacter infection. Table 2 shows the antibiotic resistance profile of Enterobacter spp during study period. Extended spectrum Beta lactamase (ESBL) producers and Multidrug resistance (MDR) are increasing in Enterobacter spp as shown in figure 2 & 3 respectively.

Figure 1: Year wise distribution of Enterobacter spp

Table 1: Age & sex structure of the study population

Age (years)	Male n(%)	Female n(%)	Total n(%)
<20	08(11.42)	5(12.82)	13(11.92)
21-40	18(25.71)	14(35.89)	32 (29.35)
41-60	26(37.14)	11(28.20)	37(33.94)
61-80	18(25.71)	6(15.38)	24(22.01)
>80	-	03(7.69)	03(2.75)
Total	70(64.22)	39(35.77)	109

Table 2: Antibiotic Resistance Profile of Enterobacter spp

Antibiotic	2017(%)	2018(%)	2019 (%) (Till June)	Total (%)
Ceftriaxone	51.72	43.90	52	49.20
Cefoperazone - Sulbactam	6.89	9.75	29.16	15.26
Piperacillin - Tazobactam	17.24	14.63	23.07	18.31
Ciprofloxacin	20.68	17.07	37.5	25.08
Amikacin	13.79	17.07	20.51	17.12
Gentamicin	20.68	17.07	37.5	25.08
Imipenam	20.68	19.51	25	21.73
Meropenam	13.79	7.31	16.66	12.58
Cotrimoxazole	37.93	36.5	47.61	40.68

Figure 2: ESBL Producers among Enterobacter spp

Figure 3: MDR isolates among Enterobacter spp

Discussion

Enterobacter is one of the commensal of the human gastrointestinal tract and in environment. The prevalence of Enterobacter infection are increasing over the years [1] and the antibiotic resistance is also on increasing trend among Enterobacter spp. In our study, totally 109 Enterobacter spp were isolated from pus samples. Over the two and half years of study period, the prevalence of Enterobacter spp among Enterobacteriaceae was on increasing trend as shown in figure1 . Enterobacter spp was one of the most common gram negative bacteria to be isolated from the pus samples[8,9] . In this study, majority of Enterobacter spp infection were from inpatients. This finding correlated with study conducted by Deboral et al ⁸. Prevalence of Enterobacter spp among Enterobacteriaceae was found to be 3.45% in our study. In a study conducted

at Nepal, the prevalence of Enterobacter spp was 1.86%[10].

In our study, the antibiotic resistance was increasing among Enterobacter spp. High level of antibiotic resistance of about 49.20% was seen for third generation cephalosporin – ceftriaxone. Similar level of resistance to ceftriaxone of about 46%, 58.8% and 56% was seen in studies done by Quarishi et al[1] , Adhikari et al[10] and Dimitrova et al[5] respectively. Antibiotic resistance to aminoglycosides Amikacin and Gentamicin were found to be 17.12% and 25.05% respectively. Study done at Bangladesh also showed similar results with resistance to amikacin of 28% and 30% resistant to gentamicin[1]. A study done at Brazil, showed about 28.6% gentamicin resistant Enterobacter spp isolates[11]. About 25.08% Enterobacter spp isolates were resistant to ciprofloxacin. Similar results were seen in studies doen by Azevedo et al at

Brazil with 21.43%[11] and 36% ciprofloxacin resistant *Enterobacter* isolates from a study done at Bangladesh[1]. Cotrimoxazole was found to be resistant among 40.68% of *Enterobacter* spp which coincides with study done at Nepal with 44.1%[10] resistance and 36% resistance from a study done at Bangladesh[1]. Piperacillin – Tazobactam was found to be resistant among 18.31% of *Enterobacter* spp isolates. Study from Nepal also showed 23.5%[10] and a Bangladesh study revealed 30%¹ of resistance. This pattern of resistance can be due to higher use of broad spectrum antibiotics. Imipenam resistance was found to be 21.73% and 12.58% of isolates were resistant to meropenam. A study from Nepal showed 8.8% resistance to Imipenam and Meropenam[10]. Cefoperazone – Sulbactam was found to be resistant in 15.26% of *Enterobacter* spp isolates in our study.

Extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) producing *Enterobacter* spp was found to be 49.20% in our study. Study done by dimitrova et al[5] and Ghanavati et al[9] also showed higher rate of esbl producers among *enterobacter* spp. Esbl producing *Enterbacter* spp were 51.72% in the year 2017 with a small dip in the year 2018 with 43.90% and again 52% in the year 2019 (till june).

Multidrug Resistant(MDR) *Enterobacter* spp poses great risk of nosocomial outbreaks which could lead to high morbidity and mortality in hospitalized patients[12–17]. MDR was found to be 14% in our study. Whereas high rate of MDR producing *Enterobacter* spp were seen in studies done at Nepal, by Dimitrova (70.2%) [5] and Nepal(52.9)[10]. Multidrug resistant *Enterobacter* spp are increasing with 10%, 15% and 17% in the years 2017,2018,2019(till June) respectively as shown in figure3.

Conclusion:

Prevalence of *Enterobacter* spp and its antimicrobial resistance are on raising trend. Therefore, the monitoring of the trend of *Enterobacter* spp infection and its antimicrobial resistance pattern should be done and strengthening of Hospital infection control practices should be practiced in order to prevent the nosocomial spread of highly multidrug resistance bacteria and also in the community.

Limitation: Our study was a Single institution study. Sampling on large population could give us more details on the *Enterobacter* infection.

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